

Teachers' Epistemic Beliefs and Didactic Practices: The Case of Teaching Writing using the Competency Based Approach in Cameroon Secondary Schools

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Abstract:- This study focuses on the analysis of teachers' epistemic beliefs, their didactic practices in the teaching of writing using the Competency Based Approach to Real Life situations (CBA-RLS). We assumed that poor performance in writing is due to poor didactic transposition which is teachers' inability to manage teaching process and apply suitable methods. I argue that teachers lack a common body of knowledge that inform their teaching.

Teachers are less concerned about the variety of action to develop effective didactic situations in writing. The participants were 100 teachers from some secondary schools in Yaoundé. A mixed method design was used to get the results. The analysis employed the Pearson correlation coefficient and multiple regressions. The results reveal significant positive correlation between epistemic beliefs, didactic practices and the development of writing competency. The result shows that teachers have a negative belief about the approach as a result of problems in transposing writing knowledge and didactic practices. Writing knowledge is not decomposed in the appropriate way. Findings suggest that teachers should dedicate time in the process of co-construction of knowledge to develop appropriate didactic situations and to predict and overcome didactic obstacles. This means that teachers need to help learners better understand how the material they learned in the course connects to real-world situations.

Keywords:- Epistemic beliefs, Didactic Transposition, Competency based Approach, teacher knowledge, didactic practices.

I. INTRODUCTION

The paradigm shift in the educational system in Cameroon and as a quick response to the law of orientation has triggered curriculum reforms to adopting the Competency Based Approach through Real-life Situations (CBA-RLS) (Chi, 2016.). The National Syllabus for Anglophone Secondary schools in Cameroon is affected by the necessary mutations of appropriate modifications to keep abreast with the changing times. Despite its importance, many learners struggle with writing and the constructivist way of teaching is not easy for teachers. As a result of this, teachers and learners attitude towards the implementation of CBA is low which is subsequently linked to their level of achievement. (Daviran 2014; Mojavezi, A. & Tamiz, 2012 as cited in Bullock, 2018). From the outset of the introduction

of CBA in Cameroon, researchers published many studies that examined the major problems that confront the implementation of CBA which was lack of preparation of the main stakeholders (Foaleng, 2014, N formi & Siewoué, 2015, Belibi, 2018, ,Njwe, 2016, Nkemeleke & Belibi 2019, Tabe 2019, Wiysahnyuy 2021). Although there are already indicators of some problems with this approach, teachers, curriculum designers are faced with three problems amongst many others; epistemic beliefs held by teachers about this approach, appropriate classroom practices and curriculum implementation which respect the objectives of this approach that need to be explored.

The first problem faced by teachers is that they have a poor epistemological belief about this approach which intend affect their practices. CBA The second problem is teachers' classroom practices which does not help learners to mobilise knowledge and encourage learners' writing competence. Efforts to present meaningful writing to the learners have been a problem and CBA requires teachers to be able to present appropriate didactic situations, tasked-based behavioural or measurable outcomes. All these are possible and determined by how a teacher presents a didactic design. A good didactic design is influenced by a number of factors; (the programme of study, classroom activities, the learners, teaching aids). As a transformer of the society, it is good to examine these conditions in a comprehensive manner under which the teachers operate in the classroom scenario. The third problem faced by teachers is implementing the curriculum (programme of study) in a way that meets the educational objectives of the programme. Teachers, curriculum designers and text books writers in implementing the programme of study focuses on how to construct knowledge (scholarly knowledge) into teaching object in the classroom and do not follow the transposition process that is required to reach knowledge actually taught in the classroom (Chavallard 1989). This process involves scholarly knowledge to textbooks, to teacher knowledge and finally to learners' knowledge (Bosch & Gason 2006). This process is important because it facilitates learning and helps teachers adopt new roles in encouraging the learners to acquire knowledge, which must be facilitated but not mechanically transmitted, and entrusting the preparation of certain tasks to the learners. From observation, and discussions with teachers, the implementation of CBA and the above problems with teaching writing amongst many others confronts teachers and learners with these difficulties and we base our assumption that this is linked to a didactic transposition problem. We hypothesise that the consequential

effects of teachers' didactic practices on writing competency are made evident in the transformation of learners' knowledge.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Teachers' Epistemic beliefs

A number of researchers have carried out studies on teachers' beliefs and their effect on the construction of knowledge. Shulman (1987) opined that the role of the teacher is important in the didactic process and as such there is needed to understand the elaborate knowledge base for teaching. Epistemological beliefs are amongst one of the first consideration to be taken in the implementation of an educational policy as it gives new insight into the teaching and learning process, it either implicitly or explicitly influence learners' belief about knowledge acquisition and curriculum development (Nespor, 1987, Schraw & Olafson, 2003, Lee & Schallert 2016). Talking about how teachers act and organise their lessons in classroom situations, Donmoyer, 2001, Tsai 2002, opined that epistemic beliefs are what defines teacher's classroom practices, how teachers make choices of content, instruction are reflected in learners' role of knowledge construction and the status of the curriculum. Also, how the teacher values knowledge and how it is being shaped in the learners is a reflection of their epistemic beliefs (Yang, Chang, an Hsu, 2008). To Chan and Elliot (2004), teaching and learning approaches preferred by teachers indicate their beliefs about the ways of teaching and learning and their beliefs assigned to the teaching and learning and teacher-students roles. Teachers' belief and value system affect their classroom status and performance by shaping their in-class instructional practices and concepts (Chen, Chan, Tang & Cheng 2009). These authors opined that there has been a shift in teaching learning conceptions from traditional teaching and learning where teaching was considered to be transfer of knowledge to the construction of knowledge.

According to Graham & Harris, 2018, classroom writing practices are further influenced by teachers' beliefs and knowledge (Graham & Harris, 2018). To Brindle et al., 2016; De Smedt et al., 2016; Hsiang & Graham, 2016; Kiuahara et al., 2009; Rietdijk et al., 2018; Troia & Graham, 2016), teachers devote more time and attention to teaching writing if they are better prepared to teach it, feel more confident in their capabilities to teach it, derive greater pleasure from teaching it, and consider it an important skill. They are also more likely to apply specific writing practices they view as acceptable (Troia & Graham, 2017).

Beliefs about the teaching of writing are involved in classroom discourse, interactions and behaviours. According to Arkoudis, 2003, language teacher's epistemic beliefs are formulated in particular socio-economic contexts leading to expectedly different teaching behaviours. Teachers' practices indicate their beliefs about language teaching and learning and their beliefs about teaching and learning will influence their class activities than a specific method they are told to follow (Kagan, 1993, Williams & Burden 1997, Riley, 2009). There are five main categories of teachers' belief about learners and learning, teaching, curriculum,

learning to teach about the self and the nature of teaching. These categories are connected with each other, contradict and indicate the complexity of belief system (Calderhead, 1996).

B. Teacher's Knowledge about writing

Very few studies exist on Didactic Transposition and the teaching of writing. Research on Didactic Transposition (Chevallard 1985, Develay 1992, Perrenoud 1998) addresses the concept, role, schemes and the criteria for knowledge to become taught knowledge and the phases (Internal and external transposition). Again, to Perrenoud, (1988), the determination of knowledge to be taught is based on the context, social needs, and characteristics of learners. Research into the importance of teacher knowledge (Shulman, 1987, Blomeke, Gustafssen and Shavelson 2015) is not clear as to what constitute teacher subject knowledge for writing. Studies based on Shulman's thinking about knowledge variations and sub categorisation, identify four types of knowledge; subject matter knowledge, general pedagogical content knowledge, and knowledge of context. Also, Banks et al 2005, Ball et al 2008 identified six domains of content pedagogical knowledge. To Shulman, teacher education course should not focus only on classroom skills but on knowledge base. There should be the intellectual bases for teaching performance (1987; 20). Shulman's findings are focused on how knowledge informs actions and how action could reshape knowledge. To Ballock, MCQuitty and McNary (2017), there exist very limited studies for teacher knowledge and the teaching of writing and those that have been carried out offered little guidance for teacher education programmes in relation to preparing teachers to be excellent teachers of writing. To Shulman (1987), teachers' knowledge is a wide range of purposes for which people write and the different kind of texts and processes that arise from those purposes. Effective teaching needs knowledge of skills, content and general pedagogical skills (Shulman 1987: 6). According to Hyland's (2007) classification of writing knowledge, there are five aspects of writing; process, system, content, genre and context knowledge. Process or metacognitive knowledge refers to declarative, procedural, conditional knowledge. Declarative knowledge is related to facts and information, procedural is knowledge about how to conduct cognitive activities, tasks and conditional knowledge refers to the when and how certain strategy is used. Content knowledge is the topic, theme that students are expected to write on (Hyland, 2003). Genre is the classification of text based on the communicative purpose which determines the context and the audience. These elements contribute to the overall performance of the learners in producing texts. Studies carried out by Gibson 2007, Bentley 2013, Wahleitthner, 2018, was based on the pedagogical content for writing and not on the subject knowledge. They opined that to be an effective writing teacher, they must have insight knowledge, they need meaningful experience. Given the importance of knowledge to writing, we may look at the knowledge teachers bring to their own writing to make them professionals.

C. Teachers' didactic practices

To Nunan (1989) In *Designing Tasks*, the aim of CBA is associated with action, learners' engagement in communicative task. These tasks are a piece of work which involves learners in comprehending, manipulating, producing or interacting in the target language while attention is paid meaning rather than on form.

To Richard and Rodgers (1986), in CBA, learners are required to develop communicative skills and tasks constitute 'information gap' and 'information transfer'. In such a case, learners will do the same tasks but each learner has different information to complete the task. The task relies on the cognitive process. According to Prabhu (1987), these tasks include; gap activities, reasoning gap activities and opinion- gap activities. To Willis (1996), learners may be asked to list, order and sort information, compare, solve a problem, share personal experience or create tasks(26-27). Talking about the methods used in teaching writing, Chi (2016), opined that the programme of Study recommends that teaching should be according to domains./Areas of Life and not taught in isolation but in integrative, eclectic and holistic way. Writing is a productive skill where learners are expected to choose a topic and write either a narrative, descriptive, expository, an argument, a letter, a speech or a report (Chi,2016p 316). Looking at the teachers' didactic practices in teaching writing, the CBA writing syllabus is based on outcome- based approach. According to Auerberch (1986), CBA syllabus is based on the theory of social constructivism where learning is regarded as occurring through social interaction. Teaching and learning is not considered to be based on pre-determine knowledge to be produced but a situation where the teacher and learners construct knowledge through the process of socialisation. Richards (2006:14) supported the view that social constructivism sees a language classroom as the world in miniature, where activities and tasks must be real and community oriented. Following the above, CBA writing should be focused on real-life situations which learners are able to use knowledge acquired to solve real life problems. The real life activities should be related to the domains and areas of life (Richard and Rodgers 1986, p.144). Also, many researchers carried out studies on the teaching methods used in the classroom. For instance, Dockrell et al., 2016; Rietdijk et al., 2018), opined that teachers do not give the necessary attention to the stages of writing. Other researchers hold the opinion that it is due to the fact

teachers do not pay attention to the process and that writing is a complex process (Brindle, Harris, Graham, & Hebert, 2016; Graham et al., 2014; Kiuahara et al., 2009).From our review of the different approaches to teaching writing, we realised that CBA makes use of a variety of methods- the eclectic approach to teaching because all the methods are an amalgamation of the different methods.

Reviewing the literature indicate the relationship between epistemic beliefs, didactic practices and the development of writing competency. However, little has been done in these areas especially in Cameroon. To help fill the research gaps, our study focuses on teachers' epistemic beliefs, didactic practices in writing and CBA in Cameroon Secondary schools. This study focuses on writing and CBA because writing is considered to be the most challenging skill amongst the four language skills. This study contributes to new knowledge relating to the teaching of writing using CBA. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions;

- What are teachers' epistemic beliefs on the implementation of the writing programme using CBA? What kind of teacher knowledge is required to design and guide students through the different forms of writing activities?
- What are teachers' didactic practices in writing?
- What are the effects of teacher's didactic practices on learners' acquisition of writing competency?

III. METHODOLOGY

The focus of this study was to examine teachers' epistemic beliefs, didactic practices in writing. With the focus of this study, it was conducted using a mixed method. The findings to be revealed were the results about teachers' epistemic beliefs, didactic practices in a writing classroom and evaluation practices using CBA. To get the data, the collection process was through questionnaires, interviews, observation of teaching and learning of writing lessons, review of the programme of work and English Language textbooks. Participants in the study were 100 teachers from Government Bilingual Secondary School in the Mfoundi Division. Writing lessons were observed on 23rd September 2022. The analysis will yield more fruits as it is examined as a systematic description of and reflection on the ways writing is done that can help teachers to guide their choices made in planning, transposing and evaluation of teaching.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS OF FINDINGS

A. Teachers’ belief about CBA and the teaching of writing

A question was asked for teachers to rate how they find teaching writing using CBA. The results are presented below;

Table 1: Teachers’ opinion on the implementation of CBA and writing

A majority of the respondents (74) attested that the teaching of writing using CBA is interesting and they are aware of this approach but do not really know how to go about it. We can interpret this finding to the fact that teachers in Cameroon have positive attitudes towards this approach despite challenges. A proper implementation strategies put in place will be profitable to the educative system and the country at large. Cameroon hopes to become an emerging nation by the year 2035 (Chi, 2016). Teachers’ way of acting in the classroom is a reflection of background of their teaching, subject matter, social contexts. Teaching may change if this variable is positive. The teaching style recommended in this approach is a facilitator, guide, and

engineer and it is learner-centred. Also, writing is not easy to teach so they trust on this CBA to help them facilitate this teaching process. Findings from the questionnaires are contradictory to classroom observation where teachers were seen being more active than the learners. Their method of questioning was not probing enough to give a clear directive to the learners. Knowing how to ask the right question is a skill that can facilitate the learning process, deepen the knowledge and understanding of learners. We could attribute this problem to the fact that teachers still practice the traditional approach to teaching and to the lack of transposition techniques demanded by CBA.

B. Teachers’ knowledge required to design and guide learners

The second objective of this study sought to find out what kind of teacher knowledge is required to guide learners through the different forms of writing exercises. The results gotten are presented below;

What kind of teacher knowledge is required to design and guide students through the different forms of writing activities?			
indicators	frequency	Percent valid	Cumulative percent
Process writing	33	33%	33%
System writing	12	12%	45%
Content writing	46	46%	91%
Genre writing	9	9%	100%
total	100	100%	

Table 2: What kind of teacher knowledge is required to design and guide students through the different forms of writing activities?

The results revealed that teachers are not aware of writing knowledge. A majority of the respondents attested that content knowledge can guide learners in the process. Content knowledge is the teacher understands of what to teach, and how to teach learners to develop writing competencies. Teachers need to possess writing knowledge that require them to own content, system, genre, process knowledge to produce suitable writing. This highlights the need for teachers to master knowledge about writing

(Hyland, 2003, p. 27). The teacher is the key person who does the pedagogical transposition in educational and teaching activities in school. Teachers need to have sufficient knowledge about a topic before beginning to write, but teachers do not consider this aspect that serious. To change CBA and writing, educative stakeholders need to change how writing is taught. Good instruction to the teaching of writing requires rich and interconnected and multidisciplinary knowledge about subject matter, classroom

techniques, learners’ learning and diversity of knowledge.(Feltovich, Prietula, & Ericsson, 2018; Grossman & McDonald, 2008; Russ, Sherin, & Sherin, 2016; Schoenfeld, 1998; Shulman, 1987). If teachers acquire the needed knowledge, vision, and commitment, they are more likely to become masterful, efficacious, and motivated writing teachers, devoting more time to teaching it. That is why it is believed that that transformation of the society begins with the teacher. Knowledge about writing can only be sufficient if teachers understand all what it takes to

produce texts. It could be through regular practices, strategies for generating, revising, editing all kinds of text and having a reflective ability and a met awareness about writing. From classroom observation, it was realised that teachers follow textbooks as their source of writing knowledge. This may be misleading because knowledge to be taught in the classroom is based on the context, social need, characteristic of the learners, Perrenoud, (1998). Teachers need to learn ways to integrate other resources into their teaching.

C. Didactic practices in teaching writing

➤ What are teachers’ didactic practices in writing?

Results of teachers’ practices and ways of doing things in writing classrooms revealed that teachers are ignorant of the way writing is taught. In terms of the approach used, the result revealed the following;

Table 3: Distribution of Teachers’ approaches in teaching writing Which approach do you use in teaching writing in your classroom?

Findings from table 3 above revealed that a majority of teachers (53%) attested that they focus on the process of composing texts by planning, drafting and revising, 40% of the respondents focused their learners to master writing mechanics, study the relationship between purpose and forms of a particular text, 38 % of teachers focused on process of writing by taking into account the social context of the text. Surprisingly, only 18% of the teachers focused their teaching on real life situations. These methods do not reflect the prescribed approaches of teaching writing in the literature reviewed and the programme of study. According to the The syllabus for the English Language to Anglophones designed by the Inspectorate-General of Education in the Ministry of Secondary Education defines and states the orientations and visions of this syllabus as being able;

to train within the framework of an emerging Cameroon by the year 2035, citizens that will have good mastery of the two official languages (English and French), deeply rooted in their cultures but open to a world in search for sustainable development and dominated by Information and Communication Technologies.

The underlying aim was to make a shift from the skill based approach to competence based approach where knowledge acquire should prepare learners to cope in any society in which they find themselves. Thus, teachers need to train learners to acquire knowledge in both stimulated and real world experience, adopt new behaviours. As a result of this, the teacher’s role is fundamental in the process of transposition. The role of the teacher consists in organising and conducting lesson in an order that will easily create learning conditions (DolzSchneuwly, Thevenaz- Christian & Wirthner 2002). This means that teachers should be able to create teaching situations, tasks which incorporate complex

situations as learners will encounter in their professional life and situations out of the classroom setting. By doing so, it makes teaching to be meaningful as there is transformation of real life situations into didactic situations. The teacher has as to blend real life situations into didactic situations which they find it challenging.

D. Organisation, planning and teaching of writing

Another important aspect of teacher's didactic practice is how teachers organise their lessons. The way they organized it has an impact on learners' comprehension and hence the development of writing competences. The results are presented in table 4 below.

1. I break down each competency into its constituent skills.				
Modalities	Frequency	Percent	Valid percent	Cumulative percent
Very much	23	23%	23%	23%
Moderate	69	69%	69%	92%
Not at all	03	03%	03%	95%
Missing	5	5%	5%	100%
Total	100	100%	100%	
2. I design authentic writing activities that provide opportunities for learners to use language in real-life situations.				
Very much	41	41%	41%	41%
Moderate	52	52%	52%	93%
Not at all	02	02%	02%	95%
Missing	5	5%	5%	100%
Total	100	100%	100%	
3. I design assessment rubrics that pinpoint students' strengths and weaknesses, and set clear performance criteria.				
Very much	55	55%	55%	55%
Moderate	37	37%	37%	92%
Not at all	3	3%	3%	95%
Missing	5	5%	5%	100%
Total	100	100%	100%	
4. I assess students and provide personalized feedback.				
Very much	67	67%	67%	67%
Moderate	21	21%	21%	88%
Not at all	7	7%	7%	95%
Missing	5	5%	5%	100%
Total	100	100%	100%	
5. I look at skills learners need to produce coherent and appropriate texts				
Very much	57	57%	57%	57%
Moderate	35	35%	35%	92%
Not at all	3	3%	3%	95%
Missing	5	5%	5%	100%
Total	100	100%	100%	

Table 4: How do you organise, plan and teach your writing lessons?

Source: Fieldwork, 2022

Findings revealed that teachers do not usually follow the different stages of writing. In terms of organizing, planning and teaching of writing lessons, 23% of the respondents posited that they very much break down each competency into its constituent skills. In terms of designing authentic writing activities that provide opportunities for learners to use language in real life situation, 41% of the

respondents attested that they very much do that, 52% of the respondents do that to a moderate extent, 2% of the respondents do not do that all. In terms of how much teachers design assessment rubrics that pinpoints students' strength and weaknesses, set clear performance criteria, 55% of the respondent attested that they very much do that, 37% of the respondents attested that they do it moderately, while

3% respondent attested they never do that all. Corroborating these findings with observation of classroom lessons, it is contradictory. Teachers asked learners to proceed in writing when they have not taught them the aims, purpose and target audience for their writing and the rhetoric. Most at times, they consider that learners have been taught writing in different classes.

In regard to how much teachers assist learners and provide personalised feedback, 67% of the respondents said they do that very much, 21% attested that they do that moderately while 7% attested that they never do that. Concerning how teachers look at the skill learners need to produce a coherent and appropriate texts, 57% of the respondents attested that they very much focus on that, 35% attested that they somewhat do that, 3% of the respondents said they never do that. These findings are contradictory to classroom observation. Teachers hardly evaluate learners at the different stages and most of the exercises given to the learners are not related to employment or to cope in the society.

The last objective of this study is to find out the effects of poor didactic transposition on learners' development of writing competency.

V. WHAT ARE THE EFFECTS OF THIS DIDACTIC TRANSPOSITION ON LEARNERS' ACQUISITION OF WRITING?

A. Development of ideas

The construction of writing knowledge seems difficult to the teachers. As a result of this is poor transposition method, there are didactic obstacles which cause learners to have difficulties to write extensively and appropriately. The required number of words at the GCE is 450-500 words for Ordinary Level and 500-550 words for the Advanced level. Learners are unable to reach these word limits as a result of poor method of transposition. The process of constructing knowledge from something scholarly to something in the classroom makes teaching easier and fosters the teachers' role as an engineer, a facilitator in CBA. Teachers do not follow the stages of knowledge construction. From the lesson observed, the didactic situations had little relation to the real world situations. The starting point of every teaching is a didactic situation. They are the means to an end in teaching. The advantage of didactic transposition in teaching is that, a teacher can easily make predictions of the obstacles that learners may face. Teachers who do not have sufficient knowledge of transfer of knowledge, development of writing ideas, cognitive abilities, critical thinking. The impact of these on writing is didactic obstacles where learners are unable to write (Bachelard 1938; Brosseau 2002).

B. Organisation, planning, teaching

Another effect of poor didactic transposition is at the level of organisation, planning of teaching sequences. Teachers didn't take time to brainstorm, activate learners' knowledge, probe them to use their past experiences to facilitate the process. As highlighted by Bosch and Gason (2006), in studying a didactic problem like the teaching of writing using CBA, it must be accounted for in all the process of the didactic transposition. Poor organisation, poor presentation of subject hinders learners to write extensively. Teachers can anticipate learning obstacles and adjust to it if they follow the stages of construction and organisation of knowledge. Also, for easy transposition of knowledge, learners need the necessary dispositive to be aware of what they know, how they categorise knowledge, and make meaning from what they learn that will enable them in and out of the school scenario. The teacher is expected to depersonalise and decontextualize knowledge.

C. Teacher knowledge

Another problem faced is that teachers do not know how to construct writing knowledge. The knowledge a teacher has constitute the pedagogical base of teachers which includes all required cognitive knowledge for creating effective teaching learning environment (Guerriero, 2017). Referencing from our findings, the choices of their activities, techniques and methods used in the classroom live much to be desired. They need to make decisions about their lesson design, activities, classroom judgement, methods of evaluation etc. In order to make informed pedagogical decisions in writing, teachers must be able analyse didactic situations, and evaluate didactic situations in connection with the social contextual situational factors, be able to connect information to the required knowledge of teaching-learning process so as to guide the teaching action. This buttresses the fact that knowledge about writing is important for writing development in taking pedagogical decisions. Teachers need meta-linguistic, content, planning and the stages of writing for the writing development. The study highlights the need for teachers' to possess writing knowledge. This finding is consistent with the results of previous studies (Hyland, 2003, p27). To enable learners produce good text, teachers must have a mastery of writing knowledge. The effect of lack of knowledge is didactic transposition problem and hence epistemological obstacles. Again, it may result to poor didactic relation. The purpose of the teaching-studying-learning process is the relation between learner and content as the whole instructional process aims to achieve the aims in the programme of work (Kansanen, & Merrii 1999). The effect of knowledge is the result of epistemological obstacles which is the faulty ways of thinking (Brousseau, 2002). The most distinct feature of language is its knowledge and its use (Chomsky, 2007). Teaching necessarily begins with a teacher's understanding of what is to be learned, what to teach and how it has to be taught to develop writing competences. (Shulman, 1987 P.7). The ability to integrate content and pedagogical knowledge is important as it enhances the capacity to apply appropriate strategies in the classroom. The key to teacher professionalism is teachers need to base their judgement on systemised body of knowledge. Teachers' knowledge in writing and CBA has to

be taken as a whole. Teachers need to have interdisciplinary knowledge, subject matter, and curriculum knowledge, knowledge of theory and pedagogical content knowledge.

VI. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This study was to find out teachers' beliefs, didactic practices and the effects of these on writing competency Based Approach to the teaching of writing. Based on the results discussed, it can be concluded that there is poor knowledge of didactic transposition of writing knowledge under the CBA in Cameroon. This is as a result of poor epistemic beliefs, poor didactic practices. This corroborates with the hypothesis that there is a significant relationship between beliefs, didactic practices and transposition. Teachers' epistemic beliefs are very important in implementing an educational policy (Nespor, 1987, Schraw&Olafson,2003, Lee &Schallert 2016). Teachers acknowledged the importance of teaching writing using CBA. But it will be of little effect if classroom practices cannot be accomplished successfully in this approach. We can argue that although teachers think the approach is interesting, they do not hold a positive belief about this approach. For instance, they know it is interesting but they cannot carry out appropriate didactic practices. The relevant literature revealed that teaching approaches preferred by teachers is indicative of their beliefs about the ways of teaching and learning (Chan & Elliot 2004, Chen, Chan, Tang & Cheng 2009)and subsequently influence the teaching process. This accounts for the poor development of learners' writing competency.

A. Didactic practices

In terms of the didactic practices, teachers still practice the traditional approach to teaching and learning. CBA encourages the constructivist view of teaching and learning.

From the result, it could be deduced that a majority of the teachers do not know the stages of writing, hence they cannot teach well and the impact is poor results. The above data revealed that teachers do not understand approaches to teaching writing and the importance that may be given to it to use it. Awareness is a precursor to effective teaching. The aim of awareness is to create better knowledge, make adjustment and improvement.

Successful transposition is possible if the teacher describes the didactic activity by demonstrating human potentials abilities, skills and clearly indicating the performance level of the activity, skills and the indicators to be achieved. The result of this finding also revealed that teachers are not interested in the process of analysing knowledge at the different stage of transposition. A majority of teachers cannot analyse the objectives, the content characteristic, knowledge in textbooks do not match with programme's objectives. With this poor background, the efficiency of writing will be partly affected as it becomes difficult to see the connection between general knowledge and professional knowledge. This finding highlights the relationship between writing knowledge, didactic practices and the development of writing competency.

From the observation, classroom didactic practices were traditional; they did not establish any relationship between real life situations and the didactic situation. We can conclude that to transpose everyday life in the classroom is difficult for the teachers. This is as a result of the fact that the necessary groundwork was not put in place for proper implementation. Real life situations are the starting point of didactic situations and actions and for effective teaching and learning. Teachers cannot create these didactic situations if they do not have knowledge of the different situations. This brings us to the notion of interdisciplinary which requires teaching-learning situations that are meaningful to the learners. Teachers must mobilise resources, knowledge, design situations that are contextualised and multi-dimensional and for this to be possible, the teachers need an interdisciplinary approach to mobilising knowledge. Findings revealed that for teachers to create these situations are problematic and situations play a pivotal role in any teaching- process. Let us consider these situations;

- Explain your visit to a restaurant
- which do you think is appropriate; people go to the university after school, others take a year or more off to work or travel
- Write a letter to the Minister of Public Health complaining about the outbreak of cholera in your locality. You are a local leader of your community.

We see clearly that we are dealing with a restaurant situation in 1, in 2 we are making judgement of an opinion while in 3, it is a letter of complaint. If we swapped the situations or contexts, the writing not does work. Again, they have different form/structure to present the information. We have used the comparison to demonstrate the characteristic difference between the skill-based syllabus and the CBA-RLS syllabus. This new approach insists on real-life situation which is a boon to comprehension. Looking at the stages of teaching writing from a didactic point of view, teachers did not plan their lessons in relation to the intended target to be achieved. According to the didactic situations there are four stages to follow; the preparation, analytical processing, synthetic processing and the evaluation. These stages must guide and direct the teachers classroom practices

As observed from the lessons, the didactic situation created in the class had no link with real life situation. According to Roegiers (2007, 2010) CBA is conceptualized around the integrative teaching/learning model called *situations-as-starting and end points*. The teacher guides learners to work on resources (knowledge and skills required by the complex situation) and carries out preliminary tasks. Simply said, resources relative to tasks that exemplify competences are, first identified; then taught and practiced separately in complex intermediary tasks; and, finally reinvested in a group of complex meaningful certification tasks. To make the transposition from classroom to the world, teachers need knowledge that provides a clear dimension of the professional world in such a way that school writing situations must reflect and be judged on the fact that learners can write, master writing mechanics, and use knowledge in real-life situations. If CBA is to be successful in Cameroon, then teachers need to change their

didactic practices, identify factors that hinder effective didactic practices, instructions and assessment techniques.

B. Organisation and planning of lesson

Though a majority of the respondents attested that they give help to learners, looking at the writing skills, we may interpret that teachers think they are doing the right thing meanwhile they still base their teaching on the traditional approach to teaching. CBA places the learners as co-constructors of their knowledge with the teacher being a guide or a facilitator. CBA assessment is based on functionality, communication and interaction. Any practices, judgement or assessment that fails to deal with real life situations is going to pose a problem in achieving competence. This study highlights the fact that how teachers represent the subject they teach impact the way they handle and develop the subject. How well students understand the topic or tasks has an effect on the organisation of ideas (Berry, 2001). Their epistemology about the approach and the nature of the subject also contributes in development of writing competency. The effect of this poor transposition and evaluation result to graduates not being able to use English effectively in their daily living because their real communication skill/ competencies were ignored (Nkwetisama, 2012). From classroom observation, teachers do not take time to follow, control and correct learners' errors. When learners follow the writing process, they produce appropriate pieces of writing. If the objectives of education are required to meet professional, economic and political interests, the forms of teacher mediation, the sequencing of teaching – learning need to be considered. Classroom writing practices are further influenced by teachers' beliefs and knowledge (Graham & Harris, 2018). The manners in which things are done in the classroom are means through which communication and learning can be achieved. Finding from the data revealed that a majority of teachers (53%) when teaching writing focus on the process of composing texts by planning, drafting and revising. Teachers need to assess learners' competency on classroom interactions.

VII. TEACHER KNOWLEDGE

Most teachers do not take this into account teachers' knowledge when teaching. Knowledge that needs to be taught and Knowledge that can be taught has to go in line with the aim/objectives, the cognitive characteristics of the learners. We can also interpret his finding to be lack of didactic transposition capabilities (the ability to analyse the transformation of scholarly knowledge that needs to be taught in textbook and the transformation of knowledge in textbooks into the one that can be taught in classroom with a sense of responsibilities.) Thus, the result is a gap between knowledge learners get in the classroom and what they encounter in the society (Nkwetisama, 2012). Teachers are not interested in analysing knowledge at the different stages of transposition. Teachers need to possess a wide variety of knowledge as it informs their actions and how teachers' actions intend shape knowledge, As a result of this poor knowledge of transposition, the process of developing writing competence is affected. Teachers need to possess pedagogical, subject knowledge (Gibson 2007, Bentley

2013, Wahleitthner, 2018). They also need to possess content, process, genre knowledge as it contributes to the overall performance of learners' writing competency (Hyland, 2003, 2007).

Taking the hypotheses of this study into account; three major recommendations can be made.

- Proper awareness and training through seminars be given to teachers which will help them develop a positive attitude. Teachers need to prepare, decompose knowledge, sequence didactic actions in a way that will take into consideration learning obstacles that may occur and prepare didactic situations that can minimise obstacles.
- One of the ways for teachers to improve on their didactic practices is to improve on the quality of teaching by reflecting on the relationship between didactic transposition and the teaching and learning process.
- CBA is a new concept and Learners teachers need to mobilise knowledge using their cognitive abilities, understanding teachers; beliefs promote the way they mobilize knowledge. It will make them more engaging and focused in the process of teaching. No wonder Brownlee, Schraw & Berthelsen (2011) opined that teachers will help learners become active in the process. It is good to think how teachers can think big to broaden their thinking. To construct knowledge, these big ideas should be based on the nature of knowledge, the quality of knowledge and the metacognition. It can as well help teachers in selecting the content. If the goal of CBA is transfer of knowledge from one context to another, then didactic transposition offers a particular way to model writing knowledge that will enable learners to be more successful in applying the material learned in the classroom outside the classroom the school context.

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